

Synthesis of Artificial Receptors having Uracil Base Pairs Linked Through Spacers Containing Ether and Ester Moieties[†]

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2,4-Bis(trimethylsilyloxy)pyrimidine and appropriately functionalized dihalides in refluxing 1,2-dichloroethane provide respective α,ω -bis(uracil-1-yl)alkane derivatives (60–65%).

Molecular recognition and catalysis, which involve the H-bonding, ion-dipole and dipole-dipole interactions as key step, are the backbone of biological processes. For recognition of nucleobases, many receptors have been synthesized¹ but models based on Watson-Crick and Hoogsteen type H-bonding interactions², prevailing in nature have scarcely been studied. Recently, recognition of adenine derivatives by

emphasizes the complementarity of ligating units and an inbuilt critical balance between flexibility and rigidity of structural components. The ether and amine linkages in crown ethers and related compounds play significant role in recognition of metal ions⁵ and facilitation of biological processes through metal ion directed self-assembly of various elements of a receptor. Ester units attribute rigidity in the framework of a receptor. In the present investigations, the synthesis of receptors (10-13) possessing two uracil units, requisite for Hoogsteen type recognition of adenine, linked through a spacer possessing two ester units and various oligoethylene glycol units, have been described.

The esterification of chloroacetic acid with diethylene glycol (2 : 1) through azeotropic distillation (Dean and Stark's apparatus) gave the diester 5, liquid, M^+ m/z 258, 260, 262 (9 : 6 : 1). Similarly, chloroacetic acid with triethylene glycol and tetraethylene glycol and 1,3-bis(hydroxymethyl)-2-methoxy-4-methylbenzene (4) gave the respective dihalides 6 (90%), 7 (95%) and 8 (70%), m.p. 67°. The structures of compounds 5-8 have been determined by their ¹H and ¹³C nmr and mass spectral data.

2,4-Bis(trimethylsilyloxy)pyrimidine 9 and 5 in refluxing dichloroethane⁶ containing iodine as catalyst gave the acyclic receptor 10 (60%), m.p. 126°, M^+ m/z 410 (M^+). Its ¹H nmr spectrum exhibits two 4H triplets (3.70, 4.31, OCH₂), 4H singlet (4.54, NCH₂) along with two doublets at 5.62 (U5-H) and 7.40 (U6-H). These spectral data and elemental analysis assign the structure 10 to this compound. Similarly, the dihalides 6-8 reacted with 9 to provide re-

crown ether-nucleotide based models³ and uridine base pairs linked through hydrocarbon spacers [(CH₂)_n, n = 7–18]⁴ has been demonstrated. The development of such receptors

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th birth anniversary
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spective acyclic receptors 11-13.

The alternative approaches involving (i) transesterification of 1-ethoxycarbonylmethyluracil (14)⁶ and (ii) esterification of 1-carboxymethyl uracil (15) with respective oligoethylene glycols under acidic conditions failed to give the respective receptors. The condensation of 15 with oligoethylene glycols by using DCC resulted in the formation of 16-adduct of 15 with DCC.

The poor solubilities of the acyclic receptors 10-13 have proved detrimental in the study of their interactions with adenine.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in capillaries and are uncorrected. ¹H nmr and ¹³C nmr spectra were run on a Bruker AC 200 MHz instrument using TMS as an internal standard. Mass and Infrared were recorded on Shimadzu GCMS-QP-2000 and PYE UNICAM SP3-300 spectrometers respectively. Elemental analysis of solid samples were performed at microanalytical laboratory, R.S.I.C., Chandigarh.

α,ω-Dihalides 5-8 : A solution of diol 1 (53 g, 0.5 mol), ClCH₂COOH (95.5 g, 1.01 mol) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (100 mg) in benzene (150 ml) was refluxed and water was removed by azeotropic distillation (using Dean and Stark apparatus). After completion of the reaction (tlc), benzene was removed under vacuum and the residue was dissolved in chloroform and washed with saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO₃. Organic layer was then separated and dried with Na₂SO₄ (anhyd.). Chloroform was distilled off and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to isolate pure dihalide 5. Similarly, diols 2-4 and chloroacetic acid gave dihalides 6-8 respectively. The dihalide 8 was purified by recrystallization from dichloromethane and hexane.

1,11-Dichloro-3,6,9-trioxa-2,10-dioxoundecane (5; 95%), (6 h), b₁₀ 172-176°; M⁺ m/z 258, 260, 262 (9 : 6 : 1); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 3.73 (4H, t, *J* 4.6 Hz, 2×CH₂), 4.09 (4H, s, 2×CH₂), 4.34, (4H, t, *J* 4.6 Hz, 2×CH₂); ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃) (normal/DEPT-135) δ 40.37 (-ve, CH₂), 64.44 (-ve, CH₂), 68.17 (-ev, CH₂), 166.66 (absent, C=O); ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 1759 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

1,14-Dichloro-3,6,9,12-tetraoxa-2,13-dioxotridecane (6; 95%), (6 h), b₁₀ 196-202°; M⁺ m/z 302, 304, 306 (9 : 6 :

1); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 3.63 (4H, s, 2×CH₂), 3.73 (4H, t, *J* 4.6 Hz, 2×CH₂), 4.09 (4H, s, 2×CH₂), 4.34 (4H, t, *J* 4.6 Hz, 2×CH₂); ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃) (normal/DEPT-135) δ 40.27 (-ve, CH₂), 64.47 (-ve, CH₂), 68.02 (-ve, CH₂), 69.83 (-ve, CH₂), 166.60 (absent, C=O); ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 1750 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

1,17-Dichloro-3,6,9,12,15-pentaoxa-2,16-dioxoheptadecane (7; 95%), (6 h), b₁₀ 218-224°; M⁺ m/z 346, 348, 350 (9 : 6 : 1); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 3.64 (8H, s, 4×CH₂), 3.72 (4H, t, *J* 4.6 Hz, 2×CH₂), 4.09 (4H, s, 2×CH₂), 4.34 (4H, t, *J* 4.6 Hz, 2×CH₂); ¹³C nmr (normal/DEPT-135) δ 40.26 (-ve, CH₂), 64.54 (-ve, CH₂), 68.13 (-ve, CH₂), 70.01 (-ve, CH₂), 166.57 (absent, C=O); ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 1750 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

Dihalide (8; 80%), (12 h), m.p. 75° (dichloromethane + hexane); M⁺ m/z 334, 336, 338 (9 : 6 : 1); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 2.32 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.10 (4H, s, 2×CH₂), 5.26 (4H, s, 2×CH₂), 7.21 (2H, s, ArH); ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃) (normal/DEPT-135) δ 20.80 (+ve, CH₃), 40.84 (-ve, CH₂), 62.96 (-ve, CH₂), 63.28 (+ve, CH₃), 128.34 (absent, C), 132.25 (+ve, C), 134.29 (absent, C), 155.57 (absent, C), 167.02 (absent, C=O); ν_{max} (KBr) 1762 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

α,ω-Bis(uracil-1-yl)alkane derivatives 10-13 : A solution of 2,4-bis(trimethylsiloxy)pyrimidine (9; 1.96 g, 0.01 mol), the alkyl dihalide (5; 0.01 mol) and I₂ (20 mg) in 1,2-dichloroethane (20 ml) was heated to reflux. After completion of the reaction (tlc), the mixture was cooled to 5° and methanol (15 ml) was added. Within few minutes a solid was separated. It was filtered and recrystallized from methanol to get pure 10. Similarly, dihalides 6-8 reacted with 9 to give 11-13 respectively. Compounds 11 and 13 were purified by recrystallisation. In case of 12, the solvent was removed from the reaction mixture and the residue was column chromatographed on silica gel (60-120 mesh) using hexane : ethyl acetate (30 : 70).

1,11-Bis(uracil-1-yl)-3,6,9-trioxa-2,10-dioxoundecane (10; 60%), (96 h), m.p. 126° (MeOH) (Found : C, 46.73; H, 4.77; N, 13.42. C₁₆H₁₈O₉N₄ requires : C, 46.82; H, 4.93; N 13.65%); M⁺ m/z 410; ¹H nmr (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) δ 3.70 (4H, t, *J* 2.2 Hz, 2×CH₂), 4.31 (4H, t, *J* 2.2 Hz, 2×CH₂), 4.54 (4H, s, 2×CH₂), 5.62 (2H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz, U5-H), 7.40 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, U6-H); ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) (normal/DEPT-135) δ 47.50 (-ve, CH₂), 63.26 (-ve, CH₂), 67.26 (-ve, CH₂), 100.58 (+ve, 5-CH), 144.06 (+ve, 6-CH), 149.95 (absent, C), 162.85 (absent, C=O), 166.66 (absent, C=O); ν_{max} (KBr) 1680 (C=O), 1702 (C=O), 1750 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

1,14-Bis(uracil-1-yl)-3,6,9,12-tetraoxa-2,13-dioxotridecane (11; 65%), (96 h), m.p. 158° (MeOH) (Found : C, 46.99; H, 4.41; N, 12.23. C₁₈H₂₂O₁₀N₄ requires : C,

47.57; H, 4.84; N, 12.33%); M^+ m/z 454 (M^+); 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$) δ 3.62 (4H, s, $2 \times CH_2$), 3.71 (4H, t, J 3.8 Hz, $2 \times CH_2$), 4.30 (4H, t, J 3.8 Hz, $2 \times CH_2$), 4.54 (4H, s, $2 \times CH_2$), 5.62 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz, U5-H), 7.45 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz, U6-H); ^{13}C nmr ($CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$) (normal/DEPT-135) δ 47.54 (-ve, CH_2), 63.60 (-ve, CH_2), 67.46 (-ve, CH_2), 69.27 (-ve, CH_2), 100.82 (+ve, 5-CH), 144.05 (+ve, 6-CH), 150.08 (absent, C=O), 163.05 (absent, C=O), 166.78 (absent, C=O); ν_{max} (KBr) 1680 (C=O), 1700 (C=O), 1750 cm^{-1} (C=O).

1,17-Bis(1-uracilyl)-3,6,9,12,15-pentaoxa-2,16-dioxoheptadecane (12; 60%), (96 h), m.p. 62° (hygroscopic); M^+ m/z 498; 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$) δ 3.66 (8H, s, $4 \times CH_2$), 3.70 (4H, t, J 4.6 Hz, $2 \times CH_2$), 4.31 (4H, t, J 4.6 Hz, $2 \times CH_2$), 4.52 (4H, s, $2 \times CH_2$), 5.64 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz, U5-H), 7.36 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz, U6-H); ^{13}C nmr ($CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$) (normal/DEPT-135) δ 46.98 (-ve, CH_2), 62.98 (-ve, CH_2), 66.62 (-ve, CH_2), 68.34 (-ve, CH_2), 68.39 (-ve, CH_2), 99.74 (+ve, 5-CH), 144.16 (+ve, 6-CH), 149.43 (absent, C=O), 162.47 (absent, C=O), 166.44 (absent, C=O); ν_{max} (KBr) 1700 (C=O), 1750 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Compound 13 : (70%), (72 h), m.p. 226° (MeOH) (Found : C, 54.59; H, 4.88; N, 11.08. $C_{28}H_{22}O_9N_4$ requires : C, 54.32; H, 4.52; N, 11.52%); M^+ m/z 486; 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ 2.32 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 3.97 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.21 (4H, s, CH_2), 5.61 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz, U5-H), 7.17 (2H, s, ArH), 7.40 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, U6-H); ^{13}C nmr ($CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$) (normal/DEPT-135) δ 19.21 (+ve, CH_3), 47.50 (+ve, CH_2), 60.75 (-ve, CH_2), 61.45 (+ve, CH_3), 100.23 (+ve, 5-CH), 126.91 (absent, C), 130.09 (+ve, Ar-CH), 132.40 (absent, C), 144.29 (+ve, 6-CH), 149.76 (absent, C), 153.50 (absent, C), 162.88 (absent, C=O), 166.46 (absent, C=O); ν_{max} (KBr) 1650 (C=O), 1710 (C=O), 1750 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Compound 16 : (70%), m.p. 172° (MeOH); M^+ m/z 376;

1H nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ 1.14–1.99 (20H, m, $10 \times CH_2$), 3.70 (1H, b s, CH), 4.02 (1H, b s, CH), 4.49 (2H, s, CH_2), 5.71 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz, U5-H), 6.97 (1H, s, NH), 7.16 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz, U6-H), 9.61 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C nmr ($CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$) (normal/DEPT-135) δ 24.63 (-ve, CH_2), 25.14 (-ve, CH_2), 25.64 (-ve, CH_2), 24.63 (-ve, CH_2), 30.27 (-ve, CH_2), 31.86 (-ve, CH_2), 33.61 (+ve, CH_3), 49.06 (-ve, CH_2), 50.10 (+ve, CH), 54.46 (+ve, CH), 101.21 (+ve, 5-CH), 145.67 (+ve, 6-CH), 151.18 (absent, C), 152.62 (absent, C), 164.22 (absent, C=O), 164.71 (absent, C=O), 184.29 (absent, C); ν_{max} (KBr) 1700 (C=O), 1676 cm^{-1} (C=O).

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